

Harnessing Technologies in Combatting Environmental Crimes: The Potential of Satellites, Drones, Water Sensors, and Super-Resolution Imaging

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Abstract

Preventing and tackling environmental crime is a global priority. The multiple risks this phenomenon poses, the high-profit margins, low risk of detection and prosecution, and the notable lack of empirical research on specific investigative practices call for innovative approaches to evidence gathering and analysis to ultimately increase the effectiveness of the fight against waste-related environmental crime.

This paper aims to shed light on the range of solutions technology can offer to improve environmental crime detection, investigation and prosecution. Ergo, this paper first presents the main procedural challenges in the uptake of technologies faced by practitioners, followed by a discussion of significant skill gaps in responding to environmental crime as identified by the UN Environmental Program, as well as by the Training Needs Assessment (TNA) and other co-creation activities undertaken within the EMERITUS project.

Secondly, the paper provides a detailed overview of the technologies and techniques EMERITUS employs in fighting environmental crime. These include satellite, drone and sensor technology, and the integration of remote sensing (RS) technologies enhanced with machine learning (ML). The paper concludes by arguing that the further employment of available super-resolution (SR) techniques can unlock the potential for more detailed environmental monitoring and analysis and is valuable for both image classification and segmentation tasks.

Keywords: waste crime, river pollution, police investigations, law enforcement agencies, earth observation.

Introduction

The term ‘waste crime’ encompasses a wide range of illegal activities throughout the entire waste management cycle, i.e., production, storage, transportation, disposal, and reuse. Waste can be defined as any material that lacks a practical purpose and is subject to permanent disposal (Baird, Curry & Cruz, 2014). Waste crime includes waste trafficking, waste dumping, the mismanagement of waste and water, and air pollution (Buczma, 2020). Indeed, these are the most common types of waste crimes, which have catastrophic effects on the environment and may seriously damage biodiversity and human health (Walters & Loureiro, 2020). Research has shown that waste crime is motivated by two primary factors: high-profit margins and unfair advantage, and low risk of detection and/or prosecution. In the most recent estimate, INTERPOL found that the average profit margin for pollution-based crime was significant, at \$19.6 million per offence (INTERPOL, 2022). Certain waste crimes, like the transnational trafficking of waste, require coordination and organisation amongst offenders, typically involving organised criminal groups (Andreatta & Favarin, 2020).

Most of all, waste crime is considered a low-risk venture (EUROPOL, 2013). The low-risk nature of engaging in waste crimes is fostered by a range of compounding factors, including an underequipped judicial system and lacklustre investigative and operational support (Lynch et al., 2016). Environmental investigative teams in law enforcement agencies (LEAs) lack specialised resources and technical devices, while multilateral law enforcement operations are not perceived as a priority vis-à-vis other forms of ‘mainstream’ crimes like drug trafficking (EUROJUST, 2014). In juxtaposition to conventional crimes, waste crime does not often involve a direct victim, and hence, early, efficient and proactive investigations are crucial for detection. It follows that a critical factor in reducing waste crime occurrence is increasing the risk of engaging in such activities.

Despite the growing recognition of waste crime as a serious global issue, there is a notable lack of empirical research exploring how law enforcement investigations can be improved. While investigative techniques of conventional crimes have received significant attention with substantial applications to policy (Gezinski, 2022), waste crime literature severely falls behind. This is unfortunate because by enhancing research in the investigation procedures employed in waste crime cases, it would be possible to better identify the challenges LEAs face, explore innovative technologies for evidence collection and analysis, and enhance the effectiveness of investigations.

Technologies can offer a range of solutions for enhancing the detection, investigation and prosecution of waste crimes, which can, in turn, increase the risk associated with engaging in such activities. Valuable yet limited forensic literature identified the potential for a range of technologies to support waste crime investigation (Alderuccio et al., 2019). Drones are one of the main technologies the literature recognises that can help fight crimes like waste dumping, water pollution, and the mismanagement of industrial waste sites (Mager & Blass, 2022), with several advantages in the investigation procedure (Sliusar et al., 2022). Satellites also offer two distinct advantages for improving the investigation of waste crimes: time series data provided via related data banks of an area photographed over several years, and quick reconnaissance of large areas using multiple sensors (Karimi et al., 2023). Recent developments in satellite technology have also increased their potential application to waste crime investigations sevenfold.

Although the extant literature pinpoints some technological applications to waste crime (Alderuccio et al., 2019; Di Fiore et al., 2017; Lega & Teta, 2016; Mager & Blass, 2022), research exploring their applications in a law enforcement context is limited. Consequently, there is a need to understand further how such technologies can be incorporated into the intricacies of waste crime investigations, encompassing the broader practical and resourcing

dimensions involved, including but not limited to the investigative strategies employed, challenges faced by LEAs, and the implications for criminal justice practices.

This paper aims to fill this knowledge gap and explore how technology (i.e., satellite, drone and sensor technology and the integration of RS technologies with ML) can be used by LEAs to enhance waste crime detection, investigation, and prosecution. The research question guiding the paper is therefore: How can technology support the investigation, forensic practice and detection of waste crimes? This topic is analysed through a literature review and the results produced within the scope of the EU-funded project EMERITUS (Environmental crimes' intelligence and investigation protocol based on multiple data sources).¹⁰

1. Identified challenges for LEAs and prosecutors in fighting environmental crimes

This section reviews the procedural challenges and barriers to the uptake of cyber-physical technologies for LEAs (1.1). An analysis of skills gap (1.2) and technical challenges (1.3) follow.

1.1 Procedural challenges and barriers

Leveraging the interviews conducted with the LEAs and Border Guards (BGs) authorities involved in the EMERITUS project, several causes emerged concerning the lack of uptake of cyber-physical technologies such as drones, satellites and sensors in the field of environmental crime – a wider category encompassing waste crime. LEAs and BGs authorities (from Italy, Spain, Greece, Romania and Moldova) identified the following factors as the most

¹⁰ The EMERITUS project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101073874.

relevant constraints: procurement-related factors, administrative/procedural aspects, resources shortage.

Regarding procurement-related factors, two critical elements were highlighted: technology cost and the administrative burden of procurement. While the former is expected to decrease over time due to technology consolidation, the latter poses a relevant problem. Being LEAs and BGs public entities, they are subject to the procurement rules dictated by European Regulation and National authorities intended to guarantee transparency and legitimacy of the public acquisition process. Yet, such procedures might result in a burdensome and time-extensive process, hampering the effective use of such technologies within certain investigation procedures.

Regarding administrative and procedural aspects, common concerns include the requirement for permits, uncertainties in data storage, and the centralisation of the deployment decision. For instance, drone usage in European urban environment is regulated by the EU Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) rules implemented by Member States, necessitating a case-by-case assessment. Specific authorisations for deviations from standard aeronautical scenarios or limitations on overflying people with certain drones may impede institutions lacking the internal expertise to evaluate aeronautical rules comprehensively. Procedural concerns arise regarding the admissibility of digital or cyber-physical evidence in court, their collection and secure storage. Satellites and drone data brought to court cannot stand alone but require supporting metadata (i.e., acquisition data and time, location, source, etc.) and, given the rise of generative artificial intelligence (AI), it is vital to protect collected digital proofs against alteration and corruption.

Resource shortage – especially technology use and maintenance expertise – is a baseline common issue entailing limited experienced drone operators and availability of drones and/or other relevant digital devices.

1.2 Skills gap

As mentioned above, environmental crime is complex in terms of definition, scope, legal framework, impacts, drivers and connections with other serious offences. Identifying and understanding the current hindrances is critical to addressing such crimes. Countries differ not only in the number and type of challenges but also in their severity (UNEP, 2018). The most significant gaps in responding to environmental crime, identified through the UN Environment Program's expert process and reinforced by the EMERITUS project, include four elements.

First is a lack of data, knowledge and awareness: the paucity of publicly available data on environmental crimes and related issues causes difficulties for governments or public organisations attempting to develop effective policies to combat such crimes.

The second issue is the insufficient and restricted application of legislation, primarily due to limited legal and administrative knowledge amongst LEAs. This results in personnel not fully aware of their enforcement authority, legal responsibilities for evidence collection, use of complementary laws, and how and to what extent information should be shared internationally.

The third is the lack of capacity in the entire enforcement chain involving investigators, prosecutors, and judges, which inhibits frontline forces responsible for combating environmental crime. This is marked by a deficiency of necessary knowledge, training and equipment to prevent environmental crimes and by the need for more sophisticated law enforcement capacity.

The fourth issue is the insufficient national and international cooperation and information sharing amongst authorities. This limitation stems from factors such as competition, mistrust, and the absence of clear institutional frameworks, hindering effective resource utilisation for combating environmental crime.

Furthermore, EMERITUS' TNA revealed that countries have different levels of training in environmental crime. Many provide training, but mostly general ones, mainly

covering theoretical knowledge. Many participants declared to be interested in receiving training in legislative matters – i.e., definitions of environmental crimes, codification of legislation, damage calculations – and on the uses and applications of cyber-physical technologies in their daily activities. A frequency-based graph was generated to visualise each proposal’s prominence. In detail, several proposals were highlighted across different domains, namely:

Legal: environmental crime identification, contaminating levels, cadastre legislation, environmental legal framework.

Ecosystemic services: measuring environmental damage on flora, fauna, water, air or soil. Effluent sampling, dumping waste, forest fire prevention and control.

Procedure: capping co-competent institutions, environmental crime reporting protocol, geo-profiling.

Tech: drone handling, satellite analysis, early fire detection, forest video-surveillance, sensors & new tech (AI, Big Data, etc.).

Figure 1. EMERITUS TNA’s results.

1.3 Technical challenges & focus on satellite images resolution

The advancement of the Earth Observation (EO) technology, including better satellite and aerial imaging, can transform environmental monitoring. Satellite and aerial images offer wide-scale perspectives unattainable by ground methods, greatly assisting environmental authorities in detecting and combating illegal waste disposal. Cross-referencing this imagery with official databases helps distinguishing legal from illegal dumping sites.

Aerial imagery has been playing an important role in analysing, monitoring and identifying waste deposits. Its initial application dates back 40 years when it was employed to estimate waste in Tampa's neighbourhoods (Garofolo et al., 1974). Despite the increasing applications of these methods over time, challenges arose due to the high costs and infrequent revisit intervals associated with aerial photogrammetric flights.

The field saw a significant shift with digital photogrammetry that enabled the creation of high-resolution (HR) digital terrain models to assess changes in waste deposits over time (Vincent et al., 1994). As technology progressed, satellite imagery began to supplement aerial imagery, offering wider coverage and better frequency. A notable example was the use of QuickBird images to identify UK illegal waste activities (Purdy et al., 2017). The success of segmentation algorithms in change detection relies on the spatial and spectral resolution of satellite imagery ensuring, respectively, detailed ground feature representation and capturing unique material properties.

Projects such as the LIFE SMART Waste project,¹¹ AI VISIONS' 'AI for Good – Landfills',¹² and the European Space Agency's Wastemon Project¹³ highlight the growing

¹¹ <http://www.lifsmartwaste.com/>.

¹² <https://www.aivisions.no/ai-for-good-landfills/>.

¹³ <https://www.planetek.it/eng/projects/wastemon>.

trend of integrating satellite data with ML to enhance waste dump detection and monitoring. Recent studies emphasised the importance of segmenting Very-High-Resolution (VHR) imagery for waste detection. Advances in deep-learning (DL) have notably enhanced satellite image segmentation methods. Techniques like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), which use multiple nonlinear layers for feature extraction and transformation, are now key in both supervised and unsupervised learning scenarios (Chen et al., 2021). These models, which integrate DL with computer vision, were effective in solid waste management applications (Ganci et al., 2021). Advancement of satellite sensors brought an influx of HR images, crucial for detecting illegal waste dumps (Notarnicola, 2004). CNNs, particularly those using Edge Boxes and multi-layered neural networks, demonstrated effective in detecting targets in satellite images of varying sizes and orientations (Katternbom, 2021).

While VHR imaging shows great promise in monitoring waste dumps, challenges remain, mainly due to the high costs of commercial data, making it not easily accessible to potential end-users. Additionally, end-users have repeatedly noted the need to detect illegal waste sites as large as 0.5 hectares, a task not feasible with only medium-resolution imagery. Applying SR algorithms to Sentinel-2 imagery is an emerging solution allowing to enhance images capped at a 10m resolution, aiding in monitoring dynamic features, environmental changes, and disaster response. The SRCNN is a DL model that has improved the spatial resolution of satellite images (Muller, 2020). Enhancement of older and current datasets can offer more detailed insights, improving long-term environmental assessments accuracy.

2. Enhanced opportunities for digital solutions

This section presents a range of technologies, i.e., satellite technology, unmanned aerial systems (UAS) and water sensors, and techniques, i.e., ML and DL, whose application is expected to empower LEAs and enhance their image analysis capabilities, thus contributing to

improved decision-making and more effective operations (2.1). Additionally, it explains that SR enhancement can be used for both classification (2.2) and segmentation (2.3) tasks.

2.1 Overview of different technologies EMERITUS employs in fighting environmental crime

In the battle against environmental crime, the combination of different RS technologies – i.e., satellites and drones – with diverse analysis techniques can significantly improve LEAs’ abilities to monitor, detect, and prevent such violations (Ferch et al., 2021; Papale et al., 2023). These technologies provide crucial insights into the location and distribution of environmental crimes.

Satellite technology, equipped with high-to-medium-resolution optical and thermal imagery, revolutionised the monitoring of environmental crimes. Thermal satellite imagery can detect elevated land surface temperatures, revealing illegal waste sites and waste burning. Additionally, Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) satellite imagery can detect changes in land topography, sewage and chemical spills, indicating illegal waste disposal.

Drones have made significant progress in waste management by complementing satellite technology. They provide HR and multiband imagery obtainable on-demand and in real-time. Drones can be remotely controlled or autonomously perform pre-programmed routes and behaviours. They can be equipped with different kinds of cameras and sensors i.e., RGB or multispectral cameras, to analyse air or gather data for 3D reconstruction. Furthermore, several drones can work collaboratively, sharing tasks and data, to scan an area, hence, reducing monitoring time. UASs can also serve as active surveillance systems to avoid disposal sites trespass and to monitor specific areas.

The integration of RS technologies with ML enables systems to learn and adapt without explicit instructions to automatically detect and classify different environmental violations, further enhancing LEAs’ capabilities to identify offenders. DL models, particularly CNNs,

have been a game-changer in image processing being able to learn and excel at visual tasks like object detection, image fusion, scene classification, land use and land cover classification in RS image analysis (Youme et al., 2021).

Moreover, technologies can also be used to tackle river pollution, a pressing global environmental issue endangering the environment and human health. Determining rivers contaminant sources is crucial for their protection and emergency response. When contaminants are released into a river, they swiftly disperse due to turbulent mixing and molecular diffusion (Wang et al., 2023) and to limit the related damages, it is vital to quickly identify contaminant source information – e.g., spill location, spill mass and release history (Kwon et al., 2021).

Optical cameras and/or satellite monitoring, along with computer vision algorithms, can automatically identify these events (Kuhn et al., 2019). However, employing water quality sensors enhances the development of more powerful detection tools. They can detect various variables, including pH levels and changes in chemical composition, extending beyond basic monitoring to identify pollution sources. Integrating this data with ML is crucial for early detection and source identification of pollution incidents. Monitoring water quality and identifying pollution sources through sensors is essential for addressing environmental crime, facilitating efficient responses, and mitigating contaminants impact over natural areas and the drinking water network.

2.2 Super-resolution for image classification

Illegal landfills are a pressing issue with significant environmental, economic and public health implications. We propose to combat this problem by leveraging aerial imagery to monitor environmental crimes through advanced image classification techniques. However, despite AI and computer vision advancements, it is still challenging to train robust ML methods

for waste detection because they need abundant aerial images of potential illegal landfills. Existing aerial landfill datasets are scarce and typically lack location information due to confidentiality agreements (Torres & Fraternali, 2023). Additionally, open-access satellite image banks like Sentinel-2 and Landsat via Copernicus¹⁴ typically provide low-resolution images with no information about potential illegal landfills.

To address the quality issue, we propose to use SR techniques to generate a HR version of a given low-resolution image (Kim, J. K. Lee & K. M. Lee, 2016a; Kim, J. K. Lee & K. M. Lee, 2016b). Consequently, this study undertakes a thorough assessment of waste detection algorithms, representing the first exploration of SR enhancement and cross-domain evaluation within the EMERITUS project. This proposal suggests utilising an HR dataset for image classification, assessing its performance across various resolutions. The goal is to evaluate how a model trained on HR images performs when applied to downsampled samples and analyse the impact of introducing SR techniques.

Throughout these experiments, we elaborate a comprehensive evaluation protocol in the field of waste detection via image classification that, to the best of our knowledge, represents a novel and unexplored avenue. Our initial results indicate the possibility of improving performance classification in a cross-domain setting with SR enhancement. Furthermore, we conduct a thorough analysis of various metrics to gain a comprehensive understanding of how these models can be tailored to specific domains.

¹⁴ Copernicus, EU's Earth Observation Programme. <https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>.

Figure 2. Example of our SR enhancement: input image (low-resolution), output (SR enhancement) and ground truth (HR).

2.3 Super-resolution for image segmentation

To overcome the scarcity of spatial resolution of freely available imagery, we propose to exploit enhanced Sentinel-2 imagery in waste analysis. The advancements in SR, with current techniques that can reconstruct HR details from low-resolution images, unlock the potential for more detailed environmental monitoring and analysis (Fernandez-Beltran, Latorre-Carmona & Pla, 2018).

Authors' contribution to this evolving field so far consisted of developing an 18 state-of-the-art SR models library that was tested in different scenarios relevant to the study of waste (Selea et al., 2023). This library encompasses a diverse array of neural network architectures, including sophisticated Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), known for their ability to generate high-quality, detailed images (Saxena & Cao, 2021); CNNs, excelling in capturing spatial hierarchies in image data (Chen et al., 2016); and Residual Networks (ResNets), effectively addressing the vanishing gradient problem and allowing for deeper and more accurate networks (He et al., 2016).

These models were trained using a vast dataset of medium-resolution images (Sentinel-2), in corroboration with VHR imagery (SPOT), to systematically upscale medium-resolution data to generate their HR equivalents. The training methodologies employed were cutting-edge, involving adversarial training that pits two networks against each other to improve generated

images quality, feature extraction capturing essential details from the low-resolution images, and residual learning helping in constructing the HR output by learning from the residuals of the low-resolution input.

Figure 3. GMV library of models implemented for SR.

This library represents a technical achievement while also serving as a resource for enhancing Sentinel-2 data. By applying these SR models to Sentinel-2 imagery, we can significantly improve resolution, making it possible to discern finer details and enhance detection and differentiation of illegal waste sites.

In our activities associated with the EMERITUS project, we have taken the first steps in integrating pre-existent own SR libraries with segmentation models. We focused on applying DL-based segmentation directly to Sentinel-2 data to identify waste dumps. This task required the segmentation models to differentiate between various land covers and to precisely outline the areas of interest. To train these models, we created a unique dataset with manually labelled masks, a necessary step due to the lack of suitable open-source datasets for this specific application.

Figure 4. Training dataset for segmentation.

Through extensive experimentation and optimisation, including hyperparameter tuning facilitated by the Optuna framework (Akiba et al., 2019), we determined the most effective combinations of models and encoders for our segmentation task. The standout combination was the DeepLabV3+ (Du, Liu & Zhang, 2021) model paired with the ResNeSt101 (Zhang et al., 2021) encoder. When applied to Sentinel-2 data, this pairing achieved a validation Intersection Over Union (IOU) score of 0.6, signifying a 60% accuracy in matching the predicted masks with the actual waste dump locations. The testing dataset yielded an IOU of 0.5 and a precision rate of 0.8, confirming the model's capability to generalise well to unseen data.

Figure 5. Inference results on different dates from a Sentinel-2 tile in Romania.

Conclusions and perspectives for further developments

This paper attempted to shed light on the range of solutions technologies can offer for enhancing the detection, investigation and prosecution of waste crimes, a serious global issue with significant environmental, economic and public health implications.

The paper first presented the main procedural challenges and barriers limiting investigative teams of LEAs' uptake of cyber-physical technologies and the most significant gaps in responding to environmental crime identified through the UN Environment Program's expert process and reinforced by the outcomes of EMERITUS' TNA. The paper then demonstrated that EO technology advancement, including better satellite and aerial imaging, can transform environmental monitoring by offering wide-scale perspectives unattainable by ground methods.

This information was complemented with a detailed overview of the technologies and techniques EMERITUS employs in fighting environmental crime. These include satellite, drone and sensor technology and the integration of RS technologies with ML that enables systems to learn and adapt without explicit instructions to automatically detect and classify different environmental violations. We concluded by claiming that the further employment of available SR techniques able to reconstruct HR details from low-resolution images can unlock the potential for more detailed environmental monitoring and analysis and is valuable for both image classification and segmentation tasks.

As we look to the future, we are poised to take the following steps: applying the described SR models to Sentinel-2 data to further enhance image resolution and, consequently, the accuracy of waste dump identification. This will involve transferring the segmentation methodology to the super-resolved imagery. By doing so, it is expected to achieve even more precise identification of smaller and less regular waste dumps, which are currently challenging to detect due to the limitations in spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 data.

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